

EXTENDED DATA

Title: Diagnostic test accuracy of screening tools for the detection of neurocognitive disorders in older adults post-trauma: A protocol for a systematic review.

Author names:

Niamh A. Merriman¹

Mary E. Walsh²

Niamh O'Regan³

Marie Carrigan⁴

Pamela Hickey⁵

Louise Brent⁶

Catherine Blake⁷

Author affiliations and contact details:

¹School of Public Health, Physiotherapy and Sports Science, University College Dublin, Dublin 4, Ireland; niamh.merriman1@ucd.ie; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5327-7762>

²School of Public Health, Physiotherapy and Sports Science, University College Dublin, Dublin 4, Ireland; m.walsh@ucd.ie; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8920-7419>

³University Hospital Waterford, Ireland; Niamh.OREgan5@hse.ie; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2510-2495>

⁴Health Information and Quality Authority, Dublin, Ireland; mcarrigan@hiqa.ie; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2940-0054>

⁵National Office of Clinical Audit, Dublin, Ireland; pamelahickey@noca.ie

⁶National Office of Clinical Audit, Dublin, Ireland; louisebrent@noca.ie; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9129-235X>

⁷School of Public Health, Physiotherapy and Sports Science, University College Dublin, Dublin 4, Ireland; c.blake@ucd.ie; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0600-629X>

Corresponding author:

Dr Niamh A. Merriman

School of Public Health, Physiotherapy and Sports Science,

University College Dublin,

Dublin 4,

Ireland

Email: niamh.merriman1@ucd.ie

Date amended: 16 April 2024

Full Search Strategy

Sources: MEDLINE (Ovid), Embase (Elsevier), PsycInfo (EBSCO), CINAHL (EBSCO), Cochrane Library (Wiley)

MEDLINE (Ovid)

Resources: Ovid MEDLINE(R) Epub Ahead of Print and Ovid MEDLINE(R) 1946 to current

1	("4AT" or "4 AT" or "4AST" or "4 AS" or "4 A S test").ti,ab.
2	"confusion assessment method".ti,ab.
3	("CAM" or "CAMICU" or "3DCAM" or "BCAM" or "UBCAM" or "UB2CAM").ti,ab.
4	("CAM-ICU" or "3D-CAM" or "B-CAM" or "UB-CAM" or "UB2-CAM").ti,ab.
5	("delirium observation screening scale" or "DOSS").ti,ab.
6	("Single Question" or "SQID" or "squid").ti,ab.
7	("recognizing acute delirium" or "recognising acute delirium" or "RADAR").ti,ab.
8	("intensive care delirium screening checklist" or "ICDSC" or "ICD-SC").ti,ab.
9	"nursing delirium screening scale".ti,ab.
10	("NUDESC" or "NU-DESC" or "NDESC" or "N DESC").ti,ab.
11	or/1-10
12	((screen* or assess* or detect* or diagnos*) adj3 (scale* or score* or tool* or test*)).ab,ti.
13	exp Mass Screening/
14	Early Diagnosis/
15	or/12-14
16	11 or 15
17	exp Delirium/
18	deliri*.ti,ab.
19	(confus* adj3 state*).ti,ab.
20	(acute* adj3 (confus* or "brain syndrome" or "brain failure")).ti,ab.
21	organic psychosyndrome.ti,ab.
22	psychoorganic syndrome.ti,ab.
23	psycho-organic syndrome.ti,ab.
24	toxic confusion*.ti,ab.
25	toxic psychosis.ti,ab.
26	or/17-25
27	exp "Sensitivity and Specificity"/
28	sensitivity.tw.
29	specificity.tw.
30	((pre-test or pretest) adj probability).tw.
31	post-test probability.tw.
32	predictive value*.tw.
33	likelihood ratio*.tw.

34	or/27-33
35	16 and 26 and 34
36	"Addenbrooke* Cognitive Exam*".ti,ab.
37	"ACE-R".ti,ab.
38	"mini-ACE".ti,ab.
39	"ACE-III".ti,ab.
40	"word recall".ti,ab.
41	("10 point cognitive screener" or "10-CS").ti,ab.
42	"7-minute screen".ti,ab.
43	"6 item cognitive impairment test".ti,ab.
44	"6 CIT".ti,ab.
45	"cognitive screen".ti,ab.
46	"abbreviated mental test".ti,ab.
47	"AMT".ti,ab.
48	"AMTS".ti,ab.
49	"ADAS-cog".ti,ab.
50	AD8.ti,ab.
51	"inform* interview".ti,ab.
52	"animal fluency test".ti,ab.
53	"brief alzheimer* screen".ti,ab.
54	"brief cognitive scale".ti,ab.
55	"clinical dementia rating scale".ti,ab.
56	"clinical dementia test".ti,ab.
57	"cognitive abilities screening instrument".ti,ab.
58	"cognitive assessment screening test".ti,ab.
59	"cognitive capacity screening examination".ti,ab.
60	"clock drawing test".ti,ab.
61	"deterioration cognitive observee".ti,ab.
62	"Dem Tect".ti,ab.
63	"fuld object memory evaluation".ti,ab.
64	"IQCODE".ti,ab.
65	"mattis dementia rating scale".ti,ab.
66	"memory impairment screen".ti,ab.
67	"minnesota cognitive acuity screen".ti,ab.
68	"mini-cog".ti,ab.
69	"mini-mental state exam*".ti,ab.
70	("mmse" or "smmse").ti,ab.
71	("modified mini-mental state exam*" or "standardised mini-mental state exam*" or "standardized mini-mental state exam*").ti,ab.
72	"montreal cognitive assessment".ti,ab.
73	"moca".ti,ab.
74	"3MS".ti,ab.
75	"neurobehavioural cognitive status exam*".ti,ab.
76	"cognistat".ti,ab.
77	"quick cognitive screening test".ti,ab.

78	"QCST".ti,ab.
79	"rapid dementia screening test".ti,ab.
80	"RDST".ti,ab.
81	"repeatable battery for the assessment of neuropsychological status".ti,ab.
82	"RBANS".ti,ab.
83	"rowland universal dementia assessment scale".ti,ab.
84	"rudas".ti,ab.
85	"self-administered gerocognitive exam*".ti,ab.
86	("self-administered" and "SAGE").ti,ab.
87	"short and sweet screening instrument".ti,ab.
88	"sassi".ti,ab.
89	"short cognitive performance test".ti,ab.
90	"syndrome kurztest".ti,ab.
91	"six item screener".ti,ab.
92	"short memory questionnaire".ti,ab.
93	"short orientation memory concentration test".ti,ab.
94	"s-omc".ti,ab.
95	"short blessed test".ti,ab.
96	"short portable mental status questionnaire".ti,ab.
97	"spmsq".ti,ab.
98	"short test of mental status".ti,ab.
99	("test your memory" or "TYM").ti,ab.
100	"trail making test".ti,ab.
101	"verbal fluency categories".ti,ab.
102	"WORLD test".ti,ab.
103	"Hopkins verbal learning test".ti,ab.
104	"HVLT".ti,ab.
105	"time and change test".ti,ab.
106	"modified world test".ti,ab.
107	"symptoms of dementia screener".ti,ab.
108	"dementia questionnaire".ti,ab.
109	"7MS".ti,ab.
110	("concord informant dementia scale" or CIDS).ti,ab.
111	(SAPH or "dementia screening and perceived harm*").ti,ab.
112	"Ottawa 3DY".ab,ti.
113	"O3DY".ab,ti.
114	or/36-113
115	15 or 114
116	exp Dementia/
117	exp Cognitive Dysfunction/ or exp Memory Disorders/
118	dementi*.ti,ab.
119	alzheimer*.ti,ab.
120	("lewy bod*" or DLB or LBD).ti,ab.

121	((cognit* or memory or cerebr* or mental*) adj3 (impair* or declin* or function* or los* or deteriorate* or degenerate* or complain* or disturb* or disorder*)).ti,ab.
122	or/116-121
123	34 and 115 and 122
124	35 or 123

Embase (Elsevier)

1	'4at':ab,ti OR '4 at':ab,ti OR '4ast':ab,ti OR '4 as':ab,ti OR '4 a s test':ab,ti
2	'confusion assessment method':ti,ab
3	'cam':ti,ab OR 'camicu':ti,ab OR '3dcam':ti,ab OR 'bcam':ti,ab OR 'ubcam':ti,ab OR 'ub2cam':ti,ab
4	'cam-icu':ti,ab OR '3d-cam':ti,ab OR 'b-cam':ti,ab OR 'ub-cam':ti,ab OR 'ub2-cam':ti,ab OR 'cam icu':ti,ab OR '3d cam':ti,ab OR 'b cam':ti,ab OR 'ub cam':ti,ab OR 'ub2 cam':ti,ab
5	'delirium observation screening scale':ti,ab OR 'doss':ti,ab
6	'single question':ti,ab OR 'sqid':ti,ab OR 'squid':ti,ab
7	'recognizing acute delirium':ti,ab OR 'recognising acute delirium':ti,ab OR 'radar':ti,ab
8	'intensive care delirium screening checklist':ti,ab OR 'icdsc':ti,ab OR 'icd-sc':ti,ab OR 'icd sc':ti,ab
9	'nursing delirium screening scale':ti,ab
10	'nudesc':ti,ab OR 'nu-desc':ti,ab OR 'ndesc':ti,ab OR 'n desc':ti,ab
11	#1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10
12	((screen* OR assess* OR detect* OR diagnos*) NEXT/3 (scale* OR score* OR tool* OR test*)):ti,ab
13	'mass screening'/exp
14	'early diagnosis'/de
15	#12 OR #13 OR #14
16	#11 OR #15
17	'delirium assessment'/de OR 'delirium'/exp
18	deliri*:ti,ab
19	(confus* NEXT/3 state*):ti,ab
20	(acute* NEXT/3 (confus* OR 'brain syndrome' OR 'brain failure')):ti,ab
21	'organic psychosyndrome':ti,ab
22	'psychoorganic syndrome':ti,ab
23	'psycho-organic syndrome':ti,ab
24	'toxic confusion*':ti,ab
25	'toxic psychosis':ti,ab
26	#17 OR #18 OR #19 OR #20 OR #21 OR #22 OR #23 OR #24 OR #25
27	#16 AND #26
28	'diagnostic accuracy'/de OR 'sensitivity and specificity'/exp
29	sensitivity:ti,ab
30	specificity:ti,ab
31	((('pre test' OR pretest) NEXT/1 probability):ti,ab
32	'post-test probability':ti,ab
33	'predictive value*':ti,ab
34	'likelihood ratio*':ti,ab
35	#17 OR #18 OR #19 OR #20 OR #21 OR #22 OR #23 OR #24 OR #25
36	#27 AND #35

37	'Addenbrooke* Cognitive Exam*':ab,ti
38	"ACE-R":ab,ti
39	'mini-ACE':ab,ti
40	'ACE-III':ab,ti
41	'word recall':ab,ti
42	'10 point cognitive screener':ab,ti OR '10-cs':ab,ti
43	'7-minute screen':ab,ti
44	'6 item cognitive impairment test':ab,ti
45	'6 CIT':ab,ti
46	'cognitive screen':ab,ti
47	'abbreviated mental test':ab,ti
48	'AMT':ab,ti
49	'AMTS':ab,ti
50	'ADAS-cog':ab,ti
51	AD8:ab,ti
52	'inform* interview':ab,ti
53	'animal fluency test':ab,ti
54	'brief alzheimer* screen':ab,ti
55	'brief cognitive scale':ab,ti
56	'clinical dementia rating scale':ab,ti
57	'clinical dementia test':ab,ti
58	'cognitive abilities screening instrument':ab,ti
59	'cognitive assessment screening test':ab,ti
60	'cognitive capacity screening examination':ab,ti
61	'clock drawing test':ab,ti
62	'deterioration cognitive observee':ab,ti
63	'Dem Tect':ab,ti
64	'fuld object memory evaluation':ab,ti
65	'IQCODE':ab,ti
66	'mattis dementia rating scale':ab,ti
67	'memory impairment screen':ab,ti
68	'minnesota cognitive acuity screen':ab,ti
69	'mini-cog':ab,ti
70	'mini-mental state examination':ab,ti
71	'mmse':ab,ti OR 'simmse':ab,ti
72	'modified mini-mental state exam':ab,ti OR 'standardised mini-mental state exam':ab,ti OR 'standardized mini-mental state exam':ab,ti
73	'montreal cognitive assessment':ab,ti
74	'moca':ab,ti
75	'3MS':ab,ti
76	'neurobehavioural cognitive status exam*':ab,ti
77	'cognistat':ab,ti
78	'quick cognitive screening test':ab,ti
79	'QCST':ab,ti
80	'rapid dementia screening test':ab,ti

81	'RDST':ab,ti
82	'repeatable battery for the assessment of neuropsychological status':ab,ti
83	'RBANS':ab,ti
84	'rowland universal dementia assessment scale':ab,ti
85	'rudas':ab,ti
86	'self-administered gerocognitive exam*':ab,ti
87	'self-administered':ab,ti AND 'sage':ab,ti
88	'short and sweet screening instrument':ab,ti
89	'sassi':ab,ti
90	'short cognitive performance test':ab,ti
91	'syndrome kurztest':ab,ti
92	'six item screener':ab,ti
93	'short memory questionnaire':ab,ti
94	'short orientation memory concentration test':ab,ti
95	's-omc':ab,ti
96	'short blessed test':ab,ti
97	'short portable mental status questionnaire':ab,ti
98	'spmsq':ab,ti
99	'short test of mental status':ab,ti
100	'test your memory':ab,ti OR 'tym':ab,ti
101	'trail making test':ab,ti
102	'verbal fluency categories':ab,ti
103	'world test':ab,ti
104	'hopkins verbal learning test':ab,ti
105	'hvl't':ab,ti
106	'time and change test':ab,ti
107	'modified world test':ab,ti
108	'symptoms of dementia screener':ab,ti
109	'dementia questionnaire':ab,ti
110	'7ms':ab,ti
111	'concord informant dementia scale':ab,ti OR cids:ab,ti
112	saph:ab,ti OR 'dementia screening and perceived harm*':ab,ti
113	'ottawa 3dy':ab,ti
114	'o3dy':ab,ti
115	#37 OR #38 OR #39 OR #40 OR #41 OR #42 OR #43 OR #44 OR #45 OR #46 OR #47 OR #48 OR #49 OR #50 OR #51 OR #52 OR #53 OR #54 OR #55 OR #56 OR #57 OR #58 OR #59 OR #60 OR #61 OR #62 OR #63 OR #64 OR #65 OR #66 OR #67 OR #68 OR #69 OR #70 OR #71 OR #72 OR #73 OR #74 OR #75 OR #76 OR #77 OR #78 OR #79 OR #80 OR #81 OR #82 OR #83 OR #84 OR #85 OR #86 OR #87 OR #88 OR #89 OR #90 OR #91 OR #92 OR #93 OR #94 OR #95 OR #96 OR #97 OR #98 OR #99 OR #100 OR #101 OR #102 OR #103 OR #104 OR #105 OR #106 OR #107 OR #108 OR #109 OR #110 OR #111 OR #112 OR #113 OR #114
116	#15 OR #115

117	'dementia'/exp
118	'cognitive defect'/exp OR 'memory disorder'/exp
119	dementi*:ab,ti
120	alzheimer*:ab,ti
121	'lewy bod*':ab,ti OR dlb:ab,ti OR lbd:ab,ti
122	((cognit* OR memory OR cerebr* OR mental*) NEXT/3 (impair* OR declin* OR function* OR los* OR deteriorate* OR degenerate* OR complain* OR disturb* OR disorder*)):ab,ti
123	#117 OR #118 OR #119 OR #120 OR #121 OR #122
124	#35 AND #116 AND #123
125	#36 OR #124
126	#125 AND [humans]/lim
127	#126 AND [medline]/lim
128	#126 NOT #127

PsycInfo (EBSCO)

S1	TI ("4AT" or "4 AT" or "4AST" or "4 AS" or "4 A S test") OR AB ("4AT" or "4 AT" or "4AST" or "4 AS" or "4 A S test")
S2	TI "confusion assessment method" OR AB "confusion assessment method"
S3	TI ("CAM" or "CAMICU" or "3DCAM" or "BCAM" or "UBCAM" or "UB2CAM") OR AB ("CAM" or "CAMICU" or "3DCAM" or "BCAM" or "UBCAM" or "UB2CAM")
S4	TI ("CAM-ICU" or "3D-CAM" or "B-CAM" or "UB-CAM" or "UB2-CAM") OR AB ("CAM-ICU" or "3D-CAM" or "B-CAM" or "UB-CAM" or "UB2-CAM")
S5	TI ("delirium observation screening scale" or "DOSS") OR AB ("delirium observation screening scale" or "DOSS")
S6	TI ("Single Question" or "SQID" or "squid") OR AB ("Single Question" or "SQID" or "squid")
S7	TI ("recognizing acute delirium" or "recognising acute delirium" or "RADAR") OR AB ("recognizing acute delirium" or "recognising acute delirium" or "RADAR")
S8	TI ("intensive care delirium screening checklist" or "ICDSC" or "ICD-SC") OR AB ("intensive care delirium screening checklist" or "ICDSC" or "ICD-SC")
S9	TI "nursing delirium screening scale" OR AB "nursing delirium screening scale"
S10	TI ("NUDESC" or "NU-DESC" or "NDESC" or "N DESC") OR AB ("NUDESC" or "NU-DESC" or "NDESC" or "N DESC")
S11	S1 OR S2 OR S3 OR S4 OR S5 OR S6 OR S7 OR S8 OR S9 OR S10
S12	TI ((screen* or assess* or detect* or diagnos*) N3 (scale* or score* or test* or tool*)) OR AB ((screen* or assess* or detect* or diagnos*) N3 (scale* or score* or test* or tool*))
S13	DE "Screening" OR DE "Screening Tests"
S14	"Early Diagnosis"
S15	S12 OR S13 OR S14
S16	S11 OR S15
S17	DE "Delirium"
S18	TI deliri* OR AB deliri*
S19	TI (confus* N3 state*) OR AB (confus* N3 state*)
S20	TI (acute* N3 (confus* or "brain syndrome" or "brain failure")) OR AB (acute* N3 (confus* or "brain syndrome" or "brain failure"))
S21	TI organic psychosyndrome OR AB organic psychosyndrome
S22	TI psychoorganic syndrome OR AB psychoorganic syndrome
S23	TI psycho-organic syndrome OR AB psycho-organic syndrome
S24	TI toxic confusion* OR AB toxic confusion*
S25	TI toxic psychosis OR AB toxic psychosis

S26	S17 OR S18 OR S19 OR S20 OR S21 OR S22 OR S23 OR S24 OR S25
S27	S16 AND S26
S28	DE "Test Sensitivity" OR DE "Test Specificity"
S29	TX sensitivity
S30	TX specificity
S31	TX ((pre-test or pretest) N1 probability)
S32	TX post-test probability
S33	TX predictive value*
S34	TX likelihood ratio*
S35	S28 OR S29 OR S30 OR S31 OR S32 OR S33 OR S34
S36	S27 AND S35
S37	TI "Addenbrooke* Cognitive Exam*" OR AB "Addenbrooke* Cognitive Exam*"
S38	TI "ACE-R" OR AB "ACE-R"
S39	TI "mini-ACE" OR AB "mini-ACE"
S40	TI "ACE-III" OR AB "ACE-III"
S41	TI "word recall" OR AB "word recall"
S42	TI "10 point cognitive screener" OR AB "10 point cognitive screener"
S43	TI "10-CS" OR AB "10-CS"
S44	TI "7-minute screen" OR AB "7-minute screen"
S45	TI "6 item cognitive impairment test" OR AB "6 item cognitive impairment test"
S46	TI "6 CIT" OR AB "6 CIT"
S47	TI "cognitive screen" OR AB "cognitive screen"
S48	TI "abbreviated mental test" OR AB "abbreviated mental test"
S49	TI "AMT" OR AB "AMT"
S50	TI "AMTS" OR AB "AMTS"
S51	TI "ADAS-cog" OR AB "ADAS-cog"
S52	TI AD8 OR AB AD8
S53	TI "inform* interview" OR AB "inform* interview"
S54	TI "animal fluency test" OR AB "animal fluency test"
S55	TI "brief alzheimer* screen" OR AB "brief alzheimer* screen"
S56	TI "brief cognitive scale" OR AB "brief cognitive scale"
S57	TI "clinical dementia rating scale" OR AB "clinical dementia rating scale"
S58	TI "clinical dementia test" OR AB "clinical dementia test"
S59	TI "cognitive abilities screening instrument" OR AB "cognitive abilities screening instrument"
S60	TI "cognitive assessment screening test" OR AB "cognitive assessment screening test"
S61	TI "cognitive capacity screening examination" OR AB "cognitive capacity screening examination"
S62	TI "clock drawing test" OR AB "clock drawing test"
S63	TI "deterioration cognitive observee" OR AB "deterioration cognitive observee"
S64	TI "Dem Tect" OR AB "Dem Tect"

S65	TI "fuld object memory evaluation" OR AB "fuld object memory evaluation"
S66	TI "IQCODE" OR AB "IQCODE"
S67	TI "mattis dementia rating scale" OR AB "mattis dementia rating scale"
S68	TI "memory impairment screen" OR AB "memory impairment screen"
S69	TI "minnesota cognitive acuity screen" OR AB "minnesota cognitive acuity screen"
S70	TI "mini-cog" OR AB "mini-cog"
S71	TI "mini-mental state exam*" OR AB "mini-mental state exam*"
S72	TI ("mmse" OR "smmse") OR AB ("mmse" OR "smmse")
S73	TI ("modified mini-mental state exam" OR "standardised mini-mental state exam" OR "standardized mini-mental state exam") OR AB ("modified mini-mental state exam" OR "standardised mini-mental state exam" OR "standardized mini-mental state exam")
S74	TI "montreal cognitive assessment" OR AB "montreal cognitive assessment"
S75	TI "moca" OR AB "moca"
S76	TI "3MS" OR AB "3MS"
S77	TI "neurobehavioural cognitive status exam*" OR AB "neurobehavioural cognitive status exam*"
S78	TI "cognistat" OR AB "cognistat"
S79	TI "quick cognitive screening test" OR AB "quick cognitive screening test"
S80	TI "QCST" OR AB "QCST"
S81	TI "rapid dementia screening test" OR AB "rapid dementia screening test"
S82	TI "RDST" OR AB "RDST"
S83	TI "repeatable battery for the assessment of neuropsychological status" OR AB "repeatable battery for the assessment of neuropsychological status"
S84	TI "RBANS" OR AB "RBANS"
S85	TI "rowland universal dementia assessment scale" OR AB "rowland universal dementia assessment scale"
S86	TI "rudas" OR AB "rudas"
S87	TI "self-administered gerocognitive exam*" OR AB "self-administered gerocognitive exam*"
S88	(TI "self-administered" OR AB "self-administered") AND (TI "SAGE" OR AB "SAGE")
S89	TI "short and sweet screening instrument" OR AB "short and sweet screening instrument"
S90	TI "sassi" OR AB "sassi"
S91	TI "short cognitive performance test" OR AB "short cognitive performance test"
S92	TI "syndrome kurztest" OR AB "syndrome kurztest"
S93	TI "six item screener" OR AB "six item screener"
S94	TI "short memory questionnaire" OR AB "short memory questionnaire"

S95	TI "short orientation memory concentration test" OR AB "short orientation memory concentration test"
S96	TI "s-omc" OR AB "s-omc"
S97	TI "short blessed test" OR AB "short blessed test"
S98	TI "short portable mental status questionnaire" OR AB "short portable mental status questionnaire"
S99	TI "spmsq" OR AB "spmsq"
S100	TI "short test of mental status" OR AB "short test of mental status"
S101	TI "test your memory" OR AB "test your memory"
S102	TI "TYM" OR AB "TYM"
S103	TI "trail making test" OR AB "trail making test"
S104	TI "verbal fluency categories" OR AB "verbal fluency categories"
S105	TI "WORLD test" OR AB "WORLD test"
S106	TI "Hopkins verbal learning test" OR AB "Hopkins verbal learning test"
S107	TI "HVL" OR AB "HVL"
S108	TI "time and change test" OR AB "time and change test"
S109	TI "modified world test" OR AB "modified world test"
S110	TI "symptoms of dementia screener" OR AB "symptoms of dementia screener"
S111	TI "dementia questionnaire" OR AB "dementia questionnaire"
S112	TI "7MS" OR AB "7MS"
S113	TI "concord informant dementia scale" OR AB "concord informant dementia scale"
S114	TI CIDS OR AB CIDS
S115	TI SAPH OR AB SAPH
S116	TI "dementia screening and perceived harm*" OR AB "dementia screening and perceived harm*"
S117	TI "Ottawa 3DY" OR AB "Ottawa 3DY"
S118	TI "O3DY" OR AB "O3DY"
S119	S37 OR S38 OR S39 OR S40 OR S41 OR S42 OR S43 OR S44 OR S45 OR S46 OR S47 OR S48 OR S49 OR S50 OR S51 OR S52 OR S53 OR S54 OR S55 OR S56 OR S57 OR S58 OR S59 OR S60 OR S61 OR S62 OR S63 OR S64 OR S65 OR S66 OR S67 OR S68 OR S69 OR S70 OR S71 OR S72 OR S73 OR S74 OR S75 OR S76 OR S77 OR S78 OR S79 OR S80 OR S81 OR S82 OR S83 OR S84 OR S85 OR S86 OR S87 OR S88 OR S89 OR S90 OR S91 OR S92 OR S93 OR S94 OR S95 OR S96 OR S97 OR S98 OR S99 OR S100 OR S101 OR S102 OR S103 OR S104 OR S105 OR S106 OR S107 OR S108 OR S109 OR S110 OR S111 OR S112 OR S113 OR S114 OR S115 OR S116 OR S117 OR S118
S120	S15 OR S119
S121	DE "Dementia" OR DE "AIDS Dementia Complex" OR DE "Alzheimer's Disease" OR DE "Dementia with Lewy Bodies" OR DE "Frontotemporal Lobar Degeneration" OR DE "Presenile Dementia" OR DE "Pseudodementia" OR DE "Senile Dementia" OR DE "Vascular Dementia"
S122	DE "Cognitive Impairment" OR DE "Memory Disorders"

S123	TI dementi* OR AB dementi*
S124	TI alzheimer* OR AB alzheimer*
S125	TI ("lewy bod*" or DLB or LBD) OR AB ("lewy bod*" or DLB or LBD)
S126	TI ((cognit* or memory or cerebr* or mental*) N3 (impair* or declin* or function* or los* or deteriorate* or degenerate* or complain* or disturb* or disorder*)) OR AB ((cognit* or memory or cerebr* or mental*) N3 (impair* or declin* or function* or los* or deteriorate* or degenerate* or complain* or disturb* or disorder*))
S127	S121 OR S122 OR S123 OR S124 OR S125 OR S126
S128	S35 AND S120 AND S127
S129	S36 OR S128

CINAHL (EBSCO)

S1	TI ("4AT" or "4 AT" or "4AST" or "4 AS" or "4 A S test") OR AB ("4AT" or "4 AT" or "4AST" or "4 AS" or "4 A S test")
S2	TI "confusion assessment method" OR AB "confusion assessment method"
S3	TI ("CAM" or "CAMICU" or "3DCAM" or "BCAM" or "UBCAM" or "UB2CAM") OR AB ("CAM" or "CAMICU" or "3DCAM" or "BCAM" or "UBCAM" or "UB2CAM")
S4	TI ("CAM-ICU" or "3D-CAM" or "B-CAM" or "UB-CAM" or "UB2-CAM") OR AB ("CAM-ICU" or "3D-CAM" or "B-CAM" or "UB-CAM" or "UB2-CAM")
S5	TI ("delirium observation screening scale" or "DOSS") OR AB ("delirium observation screening scale" or "DOSS")
S6	TI ("Single Question" or "SQID" or "squid") OR AB ("Single Question" or "SQID" or "squid")
S7	TI ("recognizing acute delirium" or "recognising acute delirium" or "RADAR") OR AB ("recognizing acute delirium" or "recognising acute delirium" or "RADAR")
S8	TI ("intensive care delirium screening checklist" or "ICDSC" or "ICD-SC") OR AB ("intensive care delirium screening checklist" or "ICDSC" or "ICD-SC")
S9	TI "nursing delirium screening scale" OR AB "nursing delirium screening scale"
S10	TI ("NUDESC" or "NU-DESC" or "NDESC" or "N DESC") OR AB ("NUDESC" or "NU-DESC" or "NDESC" or "N DESC")
S11	S1 OR S2 OR S3 OR S4 OR S5 OR S6 OR S7 OR S8 OR S9 OR S10
S12	TI (screen* N3 (test* or tool*)) OR AB (screen* N3 (test* or tool*))
S13	"mass screening"
S14	(MH "Early Diagnosis")
S15	S12 OR S13 OR S14
S16	S11 OR S15
S17	(MH "Delirium")
S18	TI deliri* OR AB deliri*
S19	TI (confus* N3 state*) OR AB (confus* N3 state*)
S20	TI (acute* N3 (confus* or "brain syndrome" or "brain failure")) OR AB (acute* N3 (confus* or "brain syndrome" or "brain failure"))
S21	TI organic psychosyndrome OR AB organic psychosyndrome
S22	TI psychoorganic syndrome OR AB psychoorganic syndrome
S23	TI psycho-organic syndrome OR AB psycho-organic syndrome
S24	TI toxic confusion* OR AB toxic confusion*
S25	TI toxic psychosis OR AB toxic psychosis
S26	S17 OR S18 OR S19 OR S20 OR S21 OR S22 OR S23 OR S24 OR S25
S27	S16 AND S26
S28	(MH "Sensitivity and Specificity")

S29	TX sensitivity
S30	TX specificity
S31	TX ((pre-test or pretest) N1 probability)
S32	TX post-test probability
S33	TX predictive value*
S34	TX likelihood ratio*
S35	S28 OR S29 OR S30 OR S31 OR S32 OR S33 OR S34
S36	S27 AND S35
S37	TI "Addenbrooke* Cognitive Exam*" OR AB "Addenbrooke* Cognitive Exam*"
S38	TI "ACE-R" OR AB "ACE-R"
S39	TI "mini-ACE" OR AB "mini-ACE"
S40	TI "ACE-III" OR AB "ACE-III"
S41	TI "word recall" OR AB "word recall"
S42	TI "10 point cognitive screener" OR AB "10 point cognitive screener"
S43	TI "10-CS" OR AB "10-CS"
S44	TI "7-minute screen" OR AB "7-minute screen"
S45	TI "6 item cognitive impairment test" OR AB "6 item cognitive impairment test"
S46	TI "6 CIT" OR AB "6 CIT"
S47	TI "cognitive screen" OR AB "cognitive screen"
S48	TI "abbreviated mental test" OR AB "abbreviated mental test"
S49	TI "AMT" OR AB "AMT"
S50	TI "AMTS" OR AB "AMTS"
S51	TI "ADAS-cog" OR AB "ADAS-cog"
S52	TI AD8 OR AB AD8
S53	TI "inform* interview" OR AB "inform* interview"
S54	TI "animal fluency test" OR AB "animal fluency test"
S55	TI "brief alzheimer* screen" OR AB "brief alzheimer* screen"
S56	TI "brief cognitive scale" OR AB "brief cognitive scale"
S57	TI "clinical dementia rating scale" OR AB "clinical dementia rating scale"
S58	TI "clinical dementia test" OR AB "clinical dementia test"
S59	TI "cognitive abilities screening instrument" OR AB "cognitive abilities screening instrument"
S60	TI "cognitive assessment screening test" OR AB "cognitive assessment screening test"
S61	TI "cognitive capacity screening examination" OR AB "cognitive capacity screening examination"
S62	TI "clock drawing test" OR AB "clock drawing test"
S63	TI "deterioration cognitive observee" OR AB "deterioration cognitive observee"
S64	TI "Dem Tect" OR AB "Dem Tect"
S65	TI "fuld object memory evaluation" OR AB "fuld object memory evaluation"
S66	TI "IQCODE" OR AB "IQCODE"

S67	TI "mattis dementia rating scale" OR AB "mattis dementia rating scale"
S68	TI "memory impairment screen" OR AB "memory impairment screen"
S69	TI "minnesota cognitive acuity screen" OR AB "minnesota cognitive acuity screen"
S70	TI "mini-cog" OR AB "mini-cog"
S71	TI "mini-mental state exam*" OR AB "mini-mental state exam*"
S72	TI ("mmse" OR "simmse") OR AB ("mmse" OR "simmse")
S73	TI ("modified mini-mental state exam" OR "standardised mini-mental state exam" OR "standardized mini-mental state exam") OR AB ("modified mini-mental state exam" OR "standardised mini-mental state exam" OR "standardized mini-mental state exam")
S74	TI "montreal cognitive assessment" OR AB "montreal cognitive assessment"
S75	TI "moca" OR AB "moca"
S76	TI "3MS" OR AB "3MS"
S77	TI "neurobehavioural cognitive status exam*" OR AB "neurobehavioural cognitive status exam*"
S78	TI "cognistat" OR AB "cognistat"
S79	TI "quick cognitive screening test" OR AB "quick cognitive screening test"
S80	TI "QCST" OR AB "QCST"
S81	TI "rapid dementia screening test" OR AB "rapid dementia screening test"
S82	TI "RDST" OR AB "RDST"
S83	TI "repeatable battery for the assessment of neuropsychological status" OR AB "repeatable battery for the assessment of neuropsychological status"
S84	TI "RBANS" OR AB "RBANS"
S85	TI "rowland universal dementia assessment scale" OR AB "rowland universal dementia assessment scale"
S86	TI "rudas" OR AB "rudas"
S87	TI "self-administered gerocognitive exam*" OR AB "self-administered gerocognitive exam*"
S88	(TI "self-administered" OR AB "self-administered") AND (TI "SAGE" OR AB "SAGE")
S89	TI "short and sweet screening instrument" OR AB "short and sweet screening instrument"
S90	TI "sassi" OR AB "sassi"
S91	TI "short cognitive performance test" OR AB "short cognitive performance test"
S92	TI "syndrome kurztest" OR AB "syndrome kurztest"
S93	TI "six item screener" OR AB "six item screener"
S94	TI "short memory questionnaire" OR AB "short memory questionnaire"
S95	TI "short orientation memory concentration test" OR AB "short orientation memory concentration test"
S96	TI "s-omc" OR AB "s-omc"

S97	TI "short blessed test" OR AB "short blessed test"
S98	TI "short portable mental status questionnaire" OR AB "short portable mental status questionnaire"
S99	TI "spmsq" OR AB "spmsq"
S100	TI "short test of mental status" OR AB "short test of mental status"
S101	TI "test your memory" OR AB "test your memory"
S102	TI "TYM" OR AB "TYM"
S103	TI "trail making test" OR AB "trail making test"
S104	TI "verbal fluency categories" OR AB "verbal fluency categories"
S105	TI "WORLD test" OR AB "WORLD test"
S106	TI "Hopkins verbal learning test" OR AB "Hopkins verbal learning test"
S107	TI "HVLТ" OR AB "HVLТ"
S108	TI "time and change test" OR AB "time and change test"
S109	TI "modified world test" OR AB "modified world test"
S110	TI "symptoms of dementia screener" OR AB "symptoms of dementia screener"
S111	TI "dementia questionnaire" OR AB "dementia questionnaire"
S112	TI "7MS" OR AB "7MS"
S113	TI "concord informant dementia scale" OR AB "concord informant dementia scale"
S114	TI CIDS OR AB CIDS
S115	TI SAPH OR AB SAPH
S116	TI "dementia screening and perceived harm*" OR AB "dementia screening and perceived harm*"
S117	TI "Ottawa 3DY" OR AB "Ottawa 3DY"
S118	TI "O3DY" OR AB "O3DY"
S119	S37 OR S38 OR S39 OR S40 OR S41 OR S42 OR S43 OR S44 OR S45 OR S46 OR S47 OR S48 OR S49 OR S50 OR S51 OR S52 OR S53 OR S54 OR S55 OR S56 OR S57 OR S58 OR S59 OR S60 OR S61 OR S62 OR S63 OR S64 OR S65 OR S66 OR S67 OR S68 OR S69 OR S70 OR S71 OR S72 OR S73 OR S74 OR S75 OR S76 OR S77 OR S78 OR S79 OR S80 OR S81 OR S82 OR S83 OR S84 OR S85 OR S86 OR S87 OR S88 OR S89 OR S90 OR S91 OR S92 OR S93 OR S94 OR S95 OR S96 OR S97 OR S98 OR S99 OR S100 OR S101 OR S102 OR S103 OR S104 OR S105 OR S106 OR S107 OR S108 OR S109 OR S110 OR S111 OR S112 OR S113 OR S114 OR S115 OR S116 OR S117 OR S118
S120	S15 OR S119
S121	(MH "Dementia+")
S122	(MH "Cognition Disorders+") OR (MH "Memory Disorders+")
S123	TI dementi* OR AB dementi*
S124	TI alzheimer* OR AB alzheimer*
S125	TI ("lewy bod*" or DLB or LBD) OR AB ("lewy bod*" or DLB or LBD)
S126	TI ((cognit* or memory or cerebr* or mental*) N3 (impair* or declin* or function* or los* or deteriorate* or degenerate* or complain* or disturb* or disorder*)) OR AB ((cognit* or memory or cerebr* or

	mental*) N3 (impair* or declin* or function* or los* or deteriorate* or degenerate* or complain* or disturb* or disorder*))
S127	S121 OR S122 OR S123 OR S124 OR S125 OR S126
S128	S35 AND S120 AND S127
S129	S36 OR S128
S130	Advanced Search function to exclude Medline

Cochrane Library (Wiley)

1	("4AT" or "4 AT" or "4AST" or "4 AS" or "4 A S test"):ti,ab
2	("confusion assessment method"):ti,ab
3	("CAM" or "CAMICU" or "3DCAM" or "BCAM" or "UBCAM" or "UB2CAM"):ti,ab
4	("CAM-ICU" or "3D-CAM" or "B-CAM" or "UB-CAM" or "UB2-CAM"):ti,ab
5	("delirium observation screening scale" or "DOSS"):ti,ab
6	("Single Question" or "SQID" or "squid"):ti,ab
7	("recognizing acute delirium" or "recognising acute delirium" or "RADAR"):ti,ab
8	("intensive care delirium screening checklist" or "ICDSC" or "ICD-SC"):ti,ab
9	("nursing delirium screening scale"):ti,ab
10	("NUDESC" or "NU-DESC" or "NDESC" or "N DESC"):ti,ab
11	{or #1-#10}
12	((screen* OR assess* OR detect* OR diagnos*) NEAR/3 (scale* OR score* OR tool* OR test*)):ti,ab
13	[mh "Mass Screening"]
14	[mh ^"Early Diagnosis"]
15	{or #12-#14}
16	#11 OR #15
17	[mh delirium]
18	deliri*:ti,ab
19	(confus* NEAR/3 state*):ti,ab
20	(acute* NEAR/3 (confus* or "brain syndrome" or "brain failure")):ti,ab
21	"organic psychosyndrome":ti,ab
22	"psychoorganic syndrome":ti,ab
23	"psycho-organic syndrome":ti,ab
24	(toxic NEXT confusion*):ti,ab
25	"toxic psychosis":ti,ab
26	{or #17-#25}
27	#16 AND #26
28	[mh "Sensitivity and Specificity"]
29	(Sensitivity):ti,ab
30	(Specificity):ti,ab
31	((pre-test OR pretest) NEXT probability):ti,ab
32	(post-test probability):ti,ab
33	(predictive value*):ti,ab
34	(likelihood ratio*):ti,ab
35	{or #28-#34}
36	#27 AND #35
37	(Addenbrooke* NEXT Cognitive NEXT Exam*):ti,ab

38	(ACE-R):ti,ab
39	(mini-ACE):ti,ab
40	(ACE-III):ti,ab
41	("word recall"):ti,ab
42	("10 point cognitive screener" OR 10 NEXT CS):ti,ab
43	("7 minute screen"):ti,ab
44	("6 item cognitive impairment test"):ti,ab
45	("6 CIT"):ti,ab
46	("cognitive screen"):ti,ab
47	("abbreviated mental test"):ti,ab
48	(AMT):ti,ab
49	(AMTS):ti,ab
50	("ADAS cog"):ti,ab
51	(AD8):ti,ab
52	(inform* NEXT interview):ti,ab
53	("animal fluency test"):ti,ab
54	(brief NEXT alzheimer* NEXT screen):ti,ab
55	("brief cognitive scale"):ti,ab
56	("clinical dementia rating scale"):ti,ab
57	("clinical dementia test"):ti,ab
58	("cognitive abilities screening instrument"):ti,ab
59	("cognitive assessment screening test"):ti,ab
60	("cognitive capacity screening examination"):ti,ab
61	("clock drawing test"):ti,ab
62	("deterioration cognitive observee"):ti,ab
63	("Dem Tect"):ti,ab
64	("fuld object memory evaluation"):ti,ab
65	("IQCODE"):ti,ab
66	("mattis dementia rating scale"):ti,ab
67	("memory impairment screen"):ti,ab
68	("minnesota cognitive acuity screen"):ti,ab
69	("mini-cog"):ti,ab
70	(mini-mental state NEXT exam*):ti,ab
71	("mmse" or "smmse"):ti,ab
72	("modified mini-mental state exam" or "standardized mini-mental state exam" or "standardised mini-mental state exam"):ti,ab
73	("montreal cognitive assessment"):ti,ab
74	("moca"):ti,ab
75	("3MS"):ti,ab
76	(neurobehavioural cognitive status NEXT exam*):ti,ab
77	("cognistat"):ti,ab
78	("quick cognitive screening test"):ti,ab
79	("QCST"):ti,ab
80	("rapid dementia screening test"):ti,ab
81	("RDST"):ti,ab

82	("repeatable battery for the assessment of neuropsychological status"):ti,ab
83	("RBANS"):ti,ab
84	("rowland universal dementia assessment scale"):ti,ab
85	("rudas"):ti,ab
86	(self-administered gerocognitive NEXT exam*):ti,ab
87	("self-administered" AND "SAGE"):ti,ab
88	("short and sweet screening instrument"):ti,ab
89	("sassi"):ti,ab
90	("short cognitive performance test"):ti,ab
91	("syndrome kurztest"):ti,ab
92	("six item screener"):ti,ab
93	("short memory questionnaire"):ti,ab
94	("short orientation memory concentration test"):ti,ab
95	("s-omc"):ti,ab
96	("short blessed test"):ti,ab
97	("short portable mental status questionnaire"):ti,ab
98	("spmsq"):ti,ab
99	("short test of mental status"):ti,ab
100	("test your memory" OR "TYM"):ti,ab
101	("trail making test"):ti,ab
102	("verbal fluency categories"):ti,ab
103	("WORLD test"):ti,ab
104	("Hopkins verbal learning test"):ti,ab
105	("HVLt"):ti,ab
106	("time and change test"):ti,ab
107	("modified world test"):ti,ab
108	("symptoms of dementia screener"):ti,ab
109	("dementia questionnaire"):ti,ab
110	("7MS"):ti,ab
111	("concord informant dementia scale" OR "CIDS"):ti,ab
112	((saph) OR (dementia screening and perceived NEXT harm*)):ti,ab
113	("Ottawa 3DY"):ti,ab
114	("O3DY"):ti,ab
115	{or #37-#114}
116	#15 OR #115
117	[mh Dementia]
118	[mh "Cognitive Dysfunction"] OR [mh "Memory Disorder"]
119	(dementi*):ti,ab
120	(alzheimer*):ti,ab
121	(lewy NEXT bod* OR (DLB OR LBD)):ti,ab
122	((cognit* or memory or cerebr* or mental*) NEAR/3 (impair* or declin* or function* or los* or deteriorate* or degenerate* or complain* or disturb* or disorder*)):ti,ab
123	{or #117-#122}

124	#35 AND #116 AND #123
125	#36 OR #124